

**A STUDY ON THE ROLE OF INTERNET MEMES IN BUILDING SOCIAL
RELATIONSHIPS AMONG GEN-Z YOUTH IN MUMBAI**

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Abstract

Internet memes are an integral part of social media culture. Its humour and connectedness to recent events makes it a popular online content. This research study aims to analyse the role internet memes play across social media platforms in building social relationships among Gen Z youth. Using a quantitative analysis method, the data was gathered using a simple random sampling method with a self-customized questionnaire shared. The data collected was from 150 self-volunteered respondents from Mumbai City. The results of the data analysis highlights the positive influence of sharing of internet memes in strengthening social bonds and increasing political and social awareness among Gen Z youth in Mumbai. The study will help psychologists and educators who seek to help youth build social bonds among their peers. The reason for the study is to help understand the importance of internet memes in the daily online discourses among Gen Z youth. Taking the focus area as Mumbai will help understand the dynamics between different thought patterns among city youth.

Keywords: *Internet memes, Gen Z youth, social relationships*

1. Introduction

The term meme was first defined by Richard Dawkins as infectious units of culture that are spread from person to person (Shifman, 2014). While this was referred by Dawkins in a biological context, there is a link between the use of the word meme and its modern understanding in defining what an internet meme is. An internet meme is defined within the context of online discourses. Memes represent small cultural elements in the form of videos, photos and audios that are repeated and remixed over a period of time, become instantly popular and fade into obscurity equally faster (Burton, 2019). In a study conducted by Leisler on memes and participatory culture, it was found that internet memes aren't searched for to understand serious topics. Rather, it is through memes that users primarily accustomed to entertainment are made aware and inclined towards discussing more serious topics, like politics (Leiser, 2022). Memes play an important role in providing cultural patterns of communication, as their viral nature and ability to embed itself into the human consciousness helps its spread become rampant and quick (Smirnova & Denissova, 2020). The Gen Z generation, that consist of individuals born between 1995 and 2012, is the first generation to have grown up in a fully connected digital world, making social media an integral part of their lives and communication methods (Siagian & Yuliana, 2023).

Research studies done on memes influence on Gen Z youth have primarily focussed on studying its role in raising political awareness among the generation. However, a study on how internet memes are also a source of building and strengthening social bonds, be it friendships or other social relationships, hasn't been done yet. This research paper, through its study on internet memes, seeks to:

1. Investigate the role of Internet memes in spreading social awareness through humour.
2. Analyse the influence of Internet memes in providing an expression of identity for Gen Z youth in the digital space.
3. Understand the moderating role of sharing a meme in strengthening social bonding among Gen Z youth.
4. Analyze the influence of expression of identity in the digital space in strengthening social bonding.

2. Literature Review

On social media platforms, humour is the one element that is sought after among its users. Most humorous content on social media that is viral in nature and also widely shared among peer is internet memes (Nueangjamnong, 2014). Since humorous content is expressed indirectly, interpretation of memes requires a shared context between the two parties. Since the memes are spread across the world via the Web, the viewer views the meme with their personal background knowledge (Vlachaki, 2020). While many internet memes these days can be very absurd to a regular viewer, there are quite some memes that require one to have a significant amount of knowledge and context of the obscure event that the meme is referring to so as to get the intended pun or humour (Partlow & Talarczyk, 2021). In a research done in 2022, participants had recorded finding happiness and amusement in internet memes especially when they were feeling down showing that memes also have a positive effect on its viewers (Balan & Aguiro, 2023).

Another aspect is how social media affected user's social and political awareness. Social media grew in popularity among youth as it provided a space for them to engage in social interactions without the restrictions of their parents. This led to a blurring between media and social space with interactions among peers happening digitally too (boyd, 2014). The interactive nature of social media has helped in users engaging in political discourses to community identity formation (Hands, 2011). Memes, like most user-generated content, mixes humour and popular culture with complex socio-political issues making it difficult to distinguish between political and non-political content (Highfield, 2016). Leiser, quoting Plevriti, holds that meme creation helps users feel that 'they can raise awareness for causes important to them' facilitating discussions on these topics. This is possible since 'memes exist as part of a communally curated media repertoire (Leiser, 2022).

Today digital media are providing young people with symbolic resources for expressing themselves and constructing their own identities (Giraldo, 2016). This adds a further challenge of creating a perfect image on these platforms (Siagian & Yuliana, 2023). Profiles created on social media are of a two-fold nature: belonging to the individual, and belonging to a collective part. They belong to the individual in the information they explicitly provide. But, they also belong to a collective part by the fact that their profiles are also determined by their friends' activities (boyd, *Its Complicated: The Social Lives of Networked Teens*, 2014). Leiser held that memes, being quick and effortless to make and share on social media, become an easy and

accessible way to share one's views on a particular matter (Leiser, 2022). Bossen held that producing content, in a way, is also a method of identity-forming where users can construct a their own image on a digital platform (Bossen & Kottasz, 2020). Shifman adds that because of this, memes also allows users to participate in collective actions while maintaining their own individuality (Shifman, 2014).

Public discourses often shape collective identity, especially for those who feel they have no support from close relations. Social Media sites, being virtual public spaces, provide a platform for building a collective identity for all, particularly these marginalized (boyd, 2007). Memes, with their often contagious humour, is a tool for culture development of collective identity formation (Wong & Holyoak, 2021). The practice of creating and sharing memes isn't just an expression of social-cultural norms but a social tool for negotiating these norms building a common ground among individuals (Gal, Shifman, & Kampf, 2016). The feeling of relatedness and belonging, which is so important for social bonding, is created through the engagement and sharing of memes. It helps create a common understanding and connect like-minded people thereby fostering a sense of community (Leiser, 2022).

A key behaviour on social media is sharing or forwarding of content. Users generally adopt this sharing behaviour so as to build a social conversation. This is usually done across platform which is known as cross-platform sharing (Ham, Lee, Hayes, & Han-Bae, 2019). A meme, in particular, is like a floating idea that is dependent on its virality. As it gets shared across cultures and contexts, it adapts itself to be reinterpreted (Gupta, 2023). And so it is observed that the success of a meme is dependent on how much viewers engage with it. This ranges from sharing the meme created to remixing and making one's own custom meme. The lifespan of a meme is dependent on how long participants interact with it (Leon & Ballesteros-Lintao, 2021). Because of its capability to be reinterpreted, memes also have the potential of shaping how users think. This could be either by reinforcing stereotypes or by introducing new ideas (Dobson & Knezevic, 2017).

The Gen Z generation is the first generation that has grown up in a fully connected digital world. Consisting of individuals born between 1995 and 2012, the Gen Z youth have made social media an integral part of the lives and communication methods (Siagian & Yuliana, 2023). Often referred to as 'digital natives', Gen Z have access to the vast wealth of information present on the online platform, particularly social media, which in turn affect their decision making and overall their psychological well-being (Sharma, Kaushal, & Joshi, 2023).

However, their exposure to the vast wealth of information makes them open to understanding and accepting different perspectives while also finding greater freedom in expressing one's views as compared to previous generations (Mahapatra, Bhullar, & Gupta, 2022). A study comparing the communication styles of Gen Z and Gen Y youth further verified that Gen Z tend to prioritize relationships over tasks when it comes to task completion (Raslie & Ting, 2021). However, it is has also been noted that due to exposure to social media at an early age, Gen Z youth are more prone to mental health problems like anxiety and depression. As a solution to these problems, Gen Z use humour as a coping mechanism as humour tends to reduce stress and increase positive emotions having benefits both physiological and psychological (Suhariningsih & Nurhayati, 2024). Memes which is one of the humorous elements of social media content becomes a way to build positive emotions.

Understanding these key aspects of how Internet memes play an influential role in the worldview of Gen Z youth, this study aims to focus on how social relationships are built and strengthened using these memes. The social relationships include friendships as well as political and social awareness. Furthermore, the sharing of memes among friends also shows how they can impact and influence social relationships among friends. The study will help psychologists and educators who seek to help youth build social bonds among their peers.

3. Methodology

Understanding the impact of memes on Gen Z youth in the digital space, the study focussed on a sample size of 110 respondents in Mumbai. Respondents belonged to three sections of Mumbai: Central Line, Harbour Line, Western Line residents. Data collection method consisted of a structured questionnaire through survey. Google forms with likert scale questions were circulated among the respondents with proper monitoring of sample collection. The study collected the sample group of respondents using the Simple Random Sampling method. Using the Chi Square method, the data collected was analysed against an expected outcome. The expected outcome was determined using the equal distribution assumption approach.

3.1 Hypothesis of the study

Based on the objectives behind the study, and the aforementioned variables, a conceptual model was developed from which seven hypotheses were developed:

Figure 1: Conceptual Map

- H₁:** Humour and satire positively influence the creation and sharing of internet memes.
- H₂:** Internet memes helps create social and political awareness
- H₃:** Internet memes helps create a space for expression of identity in the digital space.
- H₄:** Internet memes has a positive influence on Gen Z youth as a coping mechanism against negative emotions
- H₅:** Internet memes helps in strengthening social bonds.
- H₆:** Shareability of memes moderate the influence of Internet memes on strengthening social bonds among Gen Z youth.

Examining the hypotheses developed, the study aims to answer the following questions within the context of Mumbai:

- How do memes help in expressing one’s identity in the digital space?
- How do memes influence the building of friendships and social relationships?
- How are memes used to generate humour and positive emotions within individuals?

4. Data Analysis

4.1 Demographic Profile of Respondents

a. Based on Age Groups

Age	Male	Female	Prefer not to say	Total	Percentage
18-20	9	19	1	28	26.4%
21-23	13	22	0	35	31.8%
24-26	6	14	0	20	18.2%
27-29	10	15	1	26	23.6%
Total	38	70	2	110	100%

Table 1: Categorization of Respondents by Age

Figure 2: of Respondents Categorization by Age

Among the 110 respondents, **26.4%** were 20 and below, **31.8%** were between the ages 21-23, **18.2%** were between the ages 24-26, and **23.6%** were between the ages 27-29.

b. Based on Area of Residence

Area Zones in Mumbai	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Western Line	62	56.4%
Central Line	22	20%
Harbour Line	26	23.6%
Total	110	100%

Table 2: Division of Respondents according to Area of Residence

Figure 3: Division of Respondents according to Area of Residence

As seen from the pie-chart depiction, among the 110 respondents, **56.4%** were from the Western line region, **20%** were from the Central Line region, and **23.6%** were from the Harbour line region of Mumbai.

4.2 Viewing Memes motivates the Creation and Sharing of One’s Own Memes

Scales	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Strongly Agree	8	7.3%
Agree	28	25.5%
Undecided	23	20.9%

Disagree	30	27.3%
Strongly Disagree	21	19.1%
Total	110	100%

Analysis Table 1

	Observed	Expected	Difference	Difference Sq.	Diff. Sq. / Exp Fr.
Strongly Agree	8	22	-14.00	196.00	8.91
Agree	28	22	6.00	36.00	1.64
Undecided	23	22	1.00	1.00	0.05
Disagree	30	22	8.00	64.00	2.91
Strongly Disagree	21	22	-1.00	1.00	0.05
					13.545

The chi-square statistic is 13.545. The p-value is .0089.

The result is significant at $p < .05$.

Among the 110 respondents, 36 respondents (32.7%) agreed that viewing memes motivated them to create and share their own memes, while 51 respondents (46.3%) were in disagreement.

Interpretation: Based on the data collected, it is observed that memes do not fully motivate individuals to create and share their own memes, though sharing of memes is a common means of conversations over texting online.

4.3 Preference of Viewing Internet Memes over Reading the Newspaper

Scales	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Strongly Agree	17	15.5%
Agree	37	33.6%
Undecided	18	16.4%
Disagree	25	22.7%
Strongly Disagree	13	11.8%
Total	110	100%

Analysis Table 2

	Observed	Expected	Difference	Difference Sq.	Diff. Sq. / Exp Fr.
Strongly Agree	17	22	-5.00	25.00	1.14
Agree	37	22	15.00	225.00	10.23
Undecided	18	22	-4.00	16.00	0.73
Disagree	25	22	3.00	9.00	0.41
Strongly Disagree	13	22	-9.00	81.00	3.68
					16.182

The chi-square statistic is 16.182. The *p*-value is .00278.

The result is significant at $p < .05$.

When asked about whether they prefer viewing Internet Memes over reading the newspaper to be aware of the news around, 49% largely agreed with using memes as a source of news and the happening around them, and 34.5% preferred reading the newspaper to stay up-to-date with the news.

Interpretation: From the data collected, it can be seen that a large group of Gen Z tend to use memes as a source for news, while there is a considerable number of them who also prefer to stick to the traditional newspaper reading to stay abreast with the happenings around them.

4.4 Use of Internet Memes in Expressing Oneself

Scales	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Strongly Agree	19	17.3%
Agree	42	38.2%
Undecided	24	21.8%
Disagree	18	16.4%
Strongly Disagree	7	6.4%
Total	110	100%

Analysis Table 3

	Observed	Expected	Difference	Difference Sq.	Diff. Sq. / Exp Fr.
Strongly Agree	19	22	-3.00	9.00	0.41
Agree	42	22	20.00	400.00	18.18
Undecided	24	22	2.00	4.00	0.18
Disagree	18	22	-4.00	16.00	0.73
Strongly Disagree	7	22	-15.00	225.00	10.23
					29.727

The chi-square statistic is 29.727. The p-value is < .00001.

The result is significant at $p < .05$.

When asked about whether they would use memes in a situation they find difficult to express themselves, the respondents had a general agreement towards the statement. While 55.5% largely agreed with using memes to express themselves better, 22.8% disagreed using memes in expressing themselves.

Interpretation: From the data collected from the survey, it is seen that Gen Z largely tend to use internet memes to express themselves. Particularly in complex scenarios where they would find it challenging to express their emotions and views in words, they find memes as an acceptable means of expression.

4.5 Use of Internet Memes as a source for enjoyment

Scales	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Strongly Agree	31	28.2%
Agree	58	52.7%
Undecided	13	11.8%
Disagree	4	3.6%
Strongly Disagree	4	3.6%
Total	110	100%

Analysis Table 4

	Observed	Expected	Difference	Difference Sq.	Diff. Sq. / Exp Fr.
Strongly Agree	31	22	9.00	81.00	3.68
Agree	58	22	36.00	1296.00	58.91
Undecided	13	22	-9.00	81.00	3.68
Disagree	4	22	-18.00	324.00	14.73
Strongly Disagree	4	22	-18.00	324.00	14.73
					95.727

The chi-square statistic is 95.727. The p-value is < .00001.

The result is significant at $p < .05$.

When asked about how likely internet memes would be used as a mode of enjoyment and relaxation after a stressful or tiring day, 96 respondents (87.3%) agreed doing so while 14 respondents (12.7%) were in disagreement.

Interpretation: Internet memes is seen as a way through which Gen Z youth are able to seek enjoyment while also finding humour through memes as a way of overcoming the negative emotions brought up after a difficult day. Also, it goes to show how internet memes also help in depicting a difficult situation in a lighter mode.

4.6 Building of Social Bonds through responses to Internet Memes shared

Scales	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Strongly Agree	19	17.3%
Agree	39	35.5%
Slightly Agree	28	25.5%
Slightly Disagree	6	5.5%
Disagree	14	12.7%
Strongly Disagree	4	3.6%
Total	110	100%

Analysis Table 5

	Observed	Expected	Difference	Difference Sq.	Diff. Sq. / Exp Fr.
Strongly Agree	19	28	-9.00	81.00	2.89
Agree	67	28	39.00	1521.00	54.32
Disagree	20	27	-7.00	49.00	1.81
Strongly Disagree	4	27	-23.00	529.00	19.59
					78.622

The chi-square statistic is 78.622. The p-value is < .00001.

The result is significant at $p < .05$.

Among the respondents, 86 respondents (78.3%) felt that they find a greater bond being built when their friends react or respond to the memes they have shared. On the other hand, 24 respondents (21.7%) felt that they didn't feel a difference in their friendship when their friends do not respond to the memes they share.

Interpretation: It is mainly observed that the response to a meme shared among Gen Z youth, helps in building a greater bond among friends. The likeliness of a shared meme receiving a response is seen to be dependent on the level of friendship that is shared. Friendships among Gen Z youth tend to grow stronger as memes are shared and reacted or responded to.

4.7 Use of Internet Memes in Building Friendships

Scales	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Strongly Agree	18	16.4%
Agree	44	40%
Slightly Agree	27	24.5%
Slightly Disagree	8	7.3%
Disagree	10	9.1%
Strongly Disagree	3	2.7%
Total	110	100%

Analysis Table 6

	Observed	Expected	Difference	Difference Sq.	Diff. Sq. / Exp Fr.
Strongly Agree	18	28	-10.00	100.00	3.57
Agree	71	28	43.00	1849.00	66.04
Disagree	18	27	-9.00	81.00	3.00
Strongly Disagree	3	27	-24.00	576.00	21.33
					93.940

The chi-square statistic is 93.94. The p-value is < .00001.

The result is significant at $p < .05$.

Among the 110 respondents, 89 respondents (81%) felt that sharing internet memes with their friends helped them build a stronger friendship while 21 respondents (19%) were in disagreement.

Interpretation: Gen Z youth largely view Internet memes as a source for building friendships. Making it a part of their conversations online, sharing of the internet memes, for Gen Z youth, also becomes a way to keep the conversation going, thereby building and strengthening friendships among their peers.

5. Conclusion

Major Findings

Demographic Findings

- In a survey conducted, responses were collected from 110 participants, which includes 70 females and 38 males. 2 respondents preferred to not disclose their gender
 - Age group 18-21 years consisted of 28 respondents of which 9 were male, 19 were female and 1 preferred not to disclose. The number of female respondents is more than the male respondents.
 - Age group 21- 23 years consisted of 35 respondents of which 13 were male and 22 were female. The number of female respondents is more than the number of male respondents. This is also the biggest age group of respondents for the survey conducted.

- Age group 24-26 years had 20 respondents of which 6 were male and 14 were female. The number of female respondents is more than the number of male respondents
- Age group 27-29 years had 26 respondents of which 10 were male, 15 were female, and 1 preferred not to disclose. The number of female respondents is more than the male respondents.
- With regard to the area of residence, data was collected from **62** respondents (56.4%) from the Western Division of Mumbai, **22** respondents (20%) from the Central Division of Mumbai, and **26** respondents (23.6%) from the Harbour Division of Mumbai.

Remaining Findings

- A large number of respondents **agreed (55.5%)** to using internet memes to express themselves better, particularly in complex situations where they find it difficult to express themselves in words.
- The maximum number of respondents **agreed (77.3%)** towards using memes instead of text as a more likely way of communicating with friends.
- The maximum number of respondents **agreed (81%)** that they are able to build a stronger friendship when they share internet memes with their friends and peers.
- The majority of respondents **agreed (78.3%)** that they felt a greater bond being built when their friends react or respond to the memes they have shared.
- The maximum number of respondents **agreed (80%)** that they use Internet memes to stay aware of the happening around their locality.
- A large number of respondents **agreed (49%)** towards using memes as a source of news while many respondents **agreed (34.5%)** towards preferring reading the newspaper to stay abreast with current affairs.
- The maximum number of respondents **agreed (87.3%)** to using internet memes as a source of entertainment, particularly after a stressful and tiring day.

Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis	Chi-Square Value	p-Value	Hypothesis Testing	Conclusion
H₁: Humour and satire positively influence the creation and sharing of internet memes.	13.545	0.0089	$p < 0.05 \rightarrow H_0$ is rejected	Humour and satire do influence meme creation and sharing, but not necessarily in

				the ways previously assumed
H₂: Internet memes helps create social and political awareness	16.182	0.00278	p<0.05 → H ₀ is rejected	Memes are seen as a legitimate source of information, but they are not a complete substitute for traditional media like newspapers.
H₃: Internet memes helps create a space for expression of identity in the digital space.	29.727	<0.00001	p<0.05 → H ₀ is rejected	It is highly significant that memes act as an effective medium in expressing oneself, particularly in complex situations.
H₄: Internet memes has a positive influence on Gen Z youth as a coping mechanism against negative emotions.	95.727	<0.00001	p<0.05 → H ₀ is rejected	Viewing memes is seen as a widely accepted mode of enjoyment and relaxation after a stressful and tiring day.
H₅: Internet memes helps in strengthening social bonds.	78.622	<0.00001	p<0.05 → H ₀ is rejected	Memes is seen to widely serve as a means to build bonds among friends especially when there is a response or reaction to the memes shared.
H₆: Shareability of memes moderate the influence of Internet memes on strengthening social bonds among Gen Z youth.	93.94	<0.00001	p<0.05 → H ₀ is rejected	It is widely accepted that sharing of memes strongly influences the building and strengthening of social bonds among Gen Z youth

Implications and Discussions

Based on the data collected, it has been found that memes, being an intrinsic part of the communication among Gen Z youth, do play an important role in strengthening friendships and building social bonds. Sharing of memes adds to the feeling of building up a stronger friendship. Humour which is an invariable part of internet memes do motivate one to create and share their own memes, though not as rampantly as previous data has observed. This could be probably due to demographic factors and slow cultural shifts. Nevertheless, sharing of

memes created by others does create a space for expression of identity within the digital space. This is particularly seen when a Gen Z youth is in a situation that they would find difficult to express themselves in words. The use of memes, with its humour and visual content provide an easier mode of communication and expression. It is also noted that though memes do intersperse politics with humour, and is a majorly sought after means of staying abreast with current affairs among Gen Z youth. However, it hasn't fully substituted the role of traditional news sources, like the newspaper. Memes are also largely used as a coping mechanism to generate positive emotions within oneself, particularly after a tiring and difficult day. Moreover, the sharing of memes with friends followed by a response or reaction does help in building social bonds and shaping friendships.

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APPENDIX

Section 1: Demographic Details

- Name
- Gender
 - Male
 - Female
 - Other
 - Prefer not to say
- Age Group
 - 18-20
 - 21-23
 - 24-26
 - 27-29
- Occupation
 - Student
 - Salaried Employee
 - Self-Employed
 - Other:
- Which part of Mumbai are you based in?
 - Western Line
 - Central Line
 - Harbour Line

Survey Questions

1. Do you use Social Medi?
 - Yes
 - No
2. Which Social Media platform do you most frequently use?
 - Instagram
 - Twitter
 - Facebook
3. How often do you use social media during the day?
 - Less than 1 hour

- 1-2 hours
 - 3-4 hours
 - 5-6 hours
 - 7+ hours
4. Do you view memes on social media?
- Yes
 - No
 - Sometimes
5. How likely are you to view memes on social media platforms?
- Always
 - Usually
 - About Half the Time
 - Seldom
 - Never
6. I find memes hilarious and relatable
- Strongly Agree
 - Agree
 - Undecided
 - Disagree
 - Strongly Disagree
7. I like to search and view memes for my personal enjoyment
- Strongly Agree
 - Agree
 - Undecided
 - Disagree
 - Strongly Disagree
8. Viewing memes motivates me to create and share my own memes
- Strongly Agree
 - Agree
 - Undecided
 - Disagree

- Strongly Disagree

9. Memes help in knowing about the recent happenings around me

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Undecided
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

10. I use memes to share about the political situation and events around me

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Undecided
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

11. I prefer to view memes rather than read a newspaper article to know the recent happenings in my locality and the country

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Undecided
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

12. Internet memes help me to express myself better especially in complex scenarios

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Undecided
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

13. Internet memes often require that I have some background information regarding the topic

- Strongly Agree

- Agree
- Undecided
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

14. I find internet memes as a good source for expressing myself to my friends, rather than texting

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Undecided
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

15. I prefer to view memes to brighten up my mood after a tiring and stressful day

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Undecided
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

16. Internet memes helps me look at a difficult situation in a lighter mode

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Undecided
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

17. Internet memes helps me build a good friendship with others

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Undecided
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

18. Sharing of internet memes with my friends helps me build a closer connection with them

- Strongly Agree

- Agree
- Undecided
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

19. I find a greater connection when my peers respond to the memes I create and share

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Undecided
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

20. I am more likely to share memes with those who share a similar background knowledge

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Undecided
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

21. I enjoy following meme pages that create memes that I can relate with

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Undecided
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

22. I am more likely to share a more viral Internet meme than an outdated one with my friends

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Undecided
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

23. I am less likely to share a meme I don't relate with

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Undecided
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree